

Case Optimization of Recycled Concrete using Deep Learning

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Abstract: Engaging in the study and advocacy of regenerated concrete aligns with the fundamental national policy of resource conservation and environmental protection. Assisting the transformation and upgrading of our country's construction industry to achieve green, high-quality development is highly significant. Due to the rapid advancement of engineering construction technology, there is an increasing demand for concrete materials. The data were extracted and standardized based on key variables such as the source of test data, material information, test environment information, and quantitative index of material properties. Multicollinearity diagnosis was used to determine the main-influencing factors of material properties.

Keywords: Recycled aggregate concrete; Machine learning; Compressive strength

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Introduction

In recent years, with the continuous acceleration of urbanization, the number of construction projects has been increasing, and the problem of construction waste has become increasingly prominent. Especially the concrete waste in construction waste occupies a large amount of land resources, causing serious impacts on the environment and posing huge challenges to the sustainable development of cities. Therefore, how to effectively utilize construction waste resources and achieve waste reuse is one of the important issues facing the current construction engineering field. Recycled concrete (RAC), as an effective technology for utilizing construction waste resources, has received widespread attention in recent years [2,3].

The concrete that is crushed, screened, and prepared as aggregate from waste concrete is called recycled concrete [4]. Compared to traditional concrete, RAC has advantages such as low cost, environmental protection, and sustainable resource utilization. The application of RAC can not only effectively reduce the impact of construction waste on the environment, but also reduce the cost of construction projects, improve the sustainable utilization rate of resources, and meet the requirements of current sustainable development. Therefore, RAC has a wide range of application prospects in the field of construction engineering and is increasingly receiving attention and attention from researchers and

enterprises. However, due to the different sources and treatment methods of construction waste, the types and properties of aggregates in RAC vary, and their mechanical and working properties are also complex, posing certain challenges to the design and application of RAC. How to overcome these challenges and improve the performance of RAC is currently a hot and difficult research topic.

In this context, many researchers have attempted to use machine learning algorithms to predict the performance of RAC. Machine learning can learn the characteristics and performance of concrete materials through analyzing and modeling a large amount of sample data, thereby predicting the performance of recycled concrete. Compared with traditional empirical formulas, machine learning prediction models are more efficient, accurate, and universal.

In the process of concrete mix design, the main consideration is whether the concrete strength meets the engineering requirements. However, in special circumstances, more requirements may need to be put forward for the performance of concrete, such as durability, cost, and environmental friendliness of concrete. The traditional concrete mix design is mainly achieved through trial mixing, which has low efficiency, lacks universality, is not suitable for complex concrete mix design, and increases the investment of manpower and material resources. Therefore, predicting RAC performance through machine learning and combining multi-objective optimization algorithms for multi-objective optimization has become an effective means of mix proportion optimization design. This method combining machine learning and multi-objective optimization algorithms can greatly improve the efficiency of RAC in practical engineering, further promote the widespread application of RAC, promote the effective utilization of construction waste resources, and promote the sustainable development of construction projects.

Artificial Algorithms

There is a universal view in the field of machine learning that "there is no free lunch in the world", which means that Algorithm A performs better than Algorithm B on the A dataset, and it will inevitably be accompanied by Algorithm A performing weaker than Algorithm B on a specific dataset b. Therefore, when using machine learning for data prediction, it is necessary to analyze specific problems and compare and analyze multiple machine learning models for different problems to obtain better prediction results.

The models selected in this article are divided into independent models and ensemble models. The independent models use artificial neural networks (ANN), Gaussian process regression (GPR), and support vector machines (SVR); The integrated model utilizes Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (GBDT), and Extreme Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (XGBOOST), which will be described in detail below.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are computational models that simulate human brain neurons and are commonly used to solve machine learning problems such as classification, regression, and clustering. Its basic components are neurons, which communicate and compute information through connections between neurons. ANN is usually organized into multiple layers, each containing multiple neurons. The output of the previous layer serves as the input of the next layer, and the final output result is shown in Figure 1, where a represents the input, w represents the weight, b is bias, f is the transfer function, usually a nonlinear function, and t is the output of the neuron. This multi-layer structure of ANNs is called Deep Neural Networks (DNNs).

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of artificial neural network Training a neural network typically involves the following steps:

Initialize weights and biases: Weights are the strength of connections between neurons, while biases are the activation threshold of neurons. These parameters are usually randomly initialized.

Forward pass calculation: The input data is processed through a neural network for forward pass calculation. Each neuron calculates the weighted sum of its input and passes it to the next layer. The output of each layer is processed by activation functions, common activation functions include sigmoid, ReLU, etc.

Calculation error: Calculate the error based on the output and the actual label. Common error functions include mean square error Mean Squared Error (MSE), Cross Entropy, etc. Backpropagation: Based on error backpropagation, calculate the gradient for each weight and bias, and use optimization algorithms such as gradient descent to update parameters and reduce errors. Repeat steps 2-4 until the specified stop condition is reached, such as the specified number of iterations or error threshold.

Datasets

A large amount of data and literature collection work was carried out, including 1373 sets of compressive strength test data, 226 sets of electrical flux test data for testing chloride ion permeability, and 625 sets of carbonation test data for testing carbonation depth of recycled concrete. A reliable machine learning model was established to predict the compressive strength, chloride ion permeability resistance, and carbonation resistance of recycled concrete. This paper first determined the data collection standards, which are as follows:

The data in the selected literature should be complete, including the mix proportion and aggregate characteristics of recycled concrete.

The selected literature does not use chemical admixtures other than water reducing agents, and other admixtures such as air entraining agents and hardening accelerators related to data are not selected.

The selected literature data only includes recycled concrete aggregates, and other types of recycled aggregates are not selected, such as recycled brick and stone aggregates, recycled ceramic aggregates, etc.

The preparation and curing conditions for recycled concrete are standard curing room curing and water curing.

The data of recycled concrete specimens prepared using only recycled coarse aggregate (RCA), with a particle size of no less than 4.75mm. Do not use literature data that preprocesses recycled aggregates, such as physically or chemically treating recycled aggregates to remove or enhance adhesive mortar. Do not use special mixing methods, such as secondary mixing [5], tertiary mixing [6].

The compressive strength requires a cube with a side length of 100mm or 150mm, a length to diameter ratio of 2, and a diameter of the compressive strength of concrete specimens with different sizes of 100mm or 150mm cylinders is converted by the conversion factor reported by Refs. The statistics of the number of initial compressive strength datasets are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Statistical information of compressive strength dataset

parameter	Company	Range	Average	Median	standard deviation
water	kg/m ³	120–300	191	182	29
cement	kg/m ³	180–650	353	355	81
sand	kg/m ³	304–1010	685	662	128
Natural aggregates	kg/m ³	0–1462	985	842	115
recycled aggregate	kg/m ³	0–1462	1025	865	120
Fly ash	kg/m ³	0–226	27	0	51
Cement strength grade	MPa	32.5, 42.5, 52.5	-	-	-
curing time	Day	1–365	57	28	89
Aggregate substitution rate	%	0–100	51	49	39

Weighted aggregate water absorption rate	%	0.1–9.3	3	2.4	1.8
Weighted aggregate density	%	1.2-5.6	3.2	2.6	2.1
Maximum aggregate size	mm	10–40	22	20	5
compressive strength	MPa	2.2–79.6	32.7	30.5	15.3

Results and Analysis

Collinearity refers to the high correlation between independent variables that may affect the results and interpretation of multiple linear regression. Collinearity diagnosis is a method used to detect the presence of collinearity issues in multiple linear regression models. Common methods include correlation coefficient matrix method, eigenvalue method, conditional number method, and variance inflation factor (VIF) method, all of which can effectively detect collinearity problems. In this paper, the VIF method is selected for dimensionality reduction of input parameters.

Figure 2 shows the initial VIF statistics for the compressive strength dataset, electrical flux corrosion dataset, and carbonization depth dataset, respectively. It can be observed that NCA, RCA, R, WA, and D generally have VIF values much higher than 10, indicating collinearity issues. This may be due to the substitution rate being calculated through RCA and NCA, and the reason why aggregates have a higher water absorption rate is mainly due to the influence of porosity. The larger the porosity, the greater the water absorption rate. On the contrary, excessive porosity reduces the density of aggregates, resulting in excessive VIF values for RCA, NCA, R, WA, and D. Therefore, in order to reduce VIF values and reduce dimensionality, some input parameters are deleted to reduce the computational efficiency of the model. Finally, By attempting and modifying, the input parameters of the compressive strength dataset are determined to be W, C, S, FA, SC, total coarse aggregate dosage (CA), R, WA, PS, CT; The electrical flux dataset is C W, S, CA, R, FA, WA, CT ; The input parameter for carbonization data is WC, S, FA, CA, R, WA, CT, T, RH, CCO2, ET. Due to the significant environmental factors such as T and ET in the carbonization depth dataset, in order to reduce model computation time and overfitting problems in machine learning models, S, FA, and CA are removed on the basis of removing collinearity problems. Therefore, the input parameters of the carbonization dataset are WC, WA, R, CT, T, RH, CCO2, ET, After dimensionality reduction, the VIF values of all parameters are shown in Figure 2. It can be observed that the VIF values of all parameters are below 10 and there is no significant correlation.

Figure 2 Comparison of VIF values before and after dimensionality reduction processing and Figure 3 shows the statistical histogram of the parameters in the compressive strength dataset, showing the distribution of input parameters

in the dataset.

Figure 3 Histogram of Parameter Statistics for Compressive Strength Dataset and Figure 4 shows the statistical histogram of the chloride ion permeability dataset parameters, showing the distribution of various input and output parameters in the dataset.

Figure 5: Histogram of parameter statistics for the electrical flux dataset

Conclusion

This articles mainly introduces the principles of machine learning model algorithms used, constructs a database for compressive strength testing, chloride ion corrosion resistance testing, and carbonation resistance testing of recycled concrete, unifies the input and output parameters of the model, completes the dimensionality reduction processing of the input parameters, and lays a data foundation for subsequent machine learning model training.

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